

COUMARINS FROM ORCINOL DERIVATIVES: CONDENSATION OF ORCACETOPHENONE MONOMETHYL ETHER WITH ETHYL ACETATE, ETHYL PROPIONATE AND ETHYL BUTYRATE, AND MOLECULAR REARRANGEMENT OF ORCACETOPHENONE DIACETATE AND DIBENZOATE, IN PRESENCE OF METALLIC SODIUM

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Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether has been condensed with ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate in presence of metallic sodium; instead of the expected β -diketones other products are obtained to which the structures of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-4:5-dimethyl-, -3:4:5-trimethyl-, and -3-ethyl-4:5-dimethyl-3:4-dihydrocoumarin respectively, have been tentatively assigned. Molecular rearrangement of orcacetophenone diacetate in presence of metallic sodium gives 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin instead of the isomeric chromone. The formation of coumarin derivatives in the above reactions has not been observed before. Similar rearrangement of orcacetophenone dibenzoate gives the expected 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone.

An important method for the synthesis of chromones is due to Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 330 *et seq.*) and consists in the condensation of esters of aliphatic and aromatic acids with *o*-methoxyacetophenones and subsequent ring-closure of the β -diketones formed. Wittig and his co-workers (*Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88; *Annalen*, 1925, 446, 155) found that *o*-hydroxyketones condensed similarly with esters to give β -diketones. Heilbron and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1311) have also used *o*-hydroxyketones instead of the *o*-methoxyketones to obtain the desired β -diketones.

Having synthesised 7-hydroxy-2-alkyl-5-methylchromones from the β -diketones obtained by the condensation of orcacetophenone dimethyl ether with ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate (Sethna and Shab, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 211, 487) it was thought of interest to see if the monomethyl ether of orcacetophenone condensed similarly to give the desired β -diketones. Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (I) on condensation with ethyl acetate in presence of pulverised sodium, however, did not give the expected β -diketone, but a product which had the following properties.

It analysed for $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$. It did not react with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride. It gave a copper salt which was sparingly soluble in benzene. It did not give coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride immediately, but a reddish violet colour developed slowly on keeping for a few minutes. It could not be methylated with methyl iodide or dimethyl sulphate in benzene or acetone solution in presence of potassium carbonate, or with dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide and it did not get either methylated or esterified with diazomethane. It did not dissolve in sodium bicarbonate but dissolved slowly in 10% NaOH solution. The original product was obtained back on filtration and acidification of the dissolved portion after 5 minutes. On keeping overnight with 10% sodium hydroxide solution it gave orcacetophenone monomethyl ether. On heating it with a few drops of dilute hydrochloric

acid in acetic acid solution it gave a product of m.p. 118-119° which was found to be 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) on direct comparison. The same coumarin was obtained by heating the product between 155° and 160° for an hour and also by shaking the copper salt, suspended in ether, with 10% sulphuric acid for about 20 minutes. The isomeric 7-methoxy-2:5-dimethylchromone has m. p. 150-52° (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

The formation of 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin by the simple loss of a molecule of water indicates either of the two possible structures (II or III; R=H) for the condensation product. The insolubility of the product in sodium bicarbonate solution, absence of reaction with methyl iodide, dimethyl sulphate and diazomethane eliminate the possibility of the cinnamic acid structure (II, R=H). The 4-hydroxy-3:4-dihydrocoumarin structure (III, R=H) explains the various reactions mentioned above fairly well and this structure is therefore tentatively assigned to this product. 7-Hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin has also been found to decompose in presence of alkali to give oracetophenone (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

Condensation of oracetophenone monomethyl ether with ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate gave products which on heating with dilute hydrochloric acid gave 7-methoxy-3:4:5-trimethylcoumarin (IV, R=Me) and 7-methoxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (IV, R=Et) respectively, as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained by Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*) in the Kostanecki propionylation and butyrylation of oracetophenone monomethyl ether. The structures of 7-methoxy-4-hydroxy-3:4:5-trimethyl- and 7-methoxy-4-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethyl-3:4-dihydrocoumarin (III; R=Me and Et respectively) have been tentatively assigned to these condensation products. Further work is in progress.

Oracetophenone did not condense with ethyl acetate under similar conditions.

The results obtained here are of interest as the formation of such products in the condensation of *o*-hydroxy-ketones with esters has been observed for the first time.

In continuation of the previous work (Pandit and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 1) on the molecular rearrangement of some *o*-acyloxy-acylarones in presence of metallic sodium, orcacetophenone diacetate and dibenzoate have been subjected to similar rearrangement. The diacetate (i) on rearrangement gave a product which was found to be identical on direct comparison with 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin (iv), obtained by Sethna and Shah (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 239) by the Kostanecki acetylation of orcacetophenone. The product was heated with sodium carbonate solution and the compound so obtained found to be identical on direct comparison with 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin, previously prepared by Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*). This is the first instance in which the molecular rearrangement of an *o*-acyloxy-acetoarone has been found to give a coumarin derivative.

On the basis of the mechanism suggested by Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*) for the formation of 7-acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin in the Kostanecki acetylation of orcacetophenone, the following mechanism for the formation of 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin in this rearrangement may be suggested.

Orcacetophenone diacetate (i) may first give the β -diketone (ii) as a result of the migration of the *o*-acetoxy group. The *o*-hydroxy group of the β -diketone may get acetylated either through the migration of the acetoxy group from 4 to 2 (a; intramolecular reaction) or due to the contribution of an acetyl group by another orcacetophenone diacetate molecule (b; intermolecular reaction). The intermediate compound (iiiA) or (iiiB), thus formed, then gives the final product (iv) on ring-closure in the case of (iiiA) and ring-closure and hydrolysis of the acetoxy group in the case of (iiiB).

Orcacetophenone dibenzoate on molecular rearrangement gave a product which was found to be identical on direct comparison with 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone prepared by Sethna and Shah (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 601) by the Kostanecki-Robinson benzoyl-

ation of orcacetophenone. The mechanism for the formation of this compound is very likely the same as that suggested by Baker (*loc. cit.*) for the formation of chromones when an *o*-hydroxyacylarone is heated with the anhydride and the sodium salt of a fatty acid.

The intermediate β -diketones could not be isolated in either of these rearrangements.

EXPERIMENTAL

Orcacetophenone Monomethyl Ether (I).—Orcacetophenone (Hoesh, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1127) (20 g.) was dissolved in sufficient acetone and sodium hydroxide (10%, 20 c.c.) added. Dimethyl sulphate (17 g. in all) and sodium hydroxide (10%, 50 c.c.) were added in small lots alternately and the reaction mixture heated on a steam-bath all the time. The reaction mixture was finally made slightly alkaline and kept overnight. The solid which separated was filtered, dried, and crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles (17 g.), m.p. 79°; (Hoesh, *loc. cit.*) also gives the same m.p.

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-4:5-dimethyl-3:4-dihydrocoumarin (III, R=H).—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (6 g.) and ethyl acetate (13 g., excess) were added to pulverised sodium (1.5 g. ca 2 mols.) in a round-bottomed flask, fitted with a double walled condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube. The flask was cooled externally. After the initial vigour of the reaction had subsided, the reaction mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 115°-120° for 1½ hours. The flask was then cooled, a little alcohol added to decompose the excess of sodium, followed by water and the unreacted ethyl acetate removed by extraction with ether. The alkaline solution was then acidified with dilute acetic acid and the solid obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in rectangular prisms (3 g.), m.p. 140-42°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 6.4. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.9; H, 6.3 per cent).

The *copper salt* was prepared by dissolving the acid in ether and shaking for half an hour with a strong solution of copper acetate. Pale green crystalline product separated which was filtered, washed with water and dried, m.p. 220-22°. It is very sparingly soluble in benzene. (Found: C, 54.9; H, 5.8. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4Cu, H_2O$ requires C, 54.8; H, 5.3 per cent).

Heating with dilute HCl and alone.—The dihydrocoumarin (III, R=H; 0.5 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and refluxed for 15 minutes with hydrochloric acid (conc., 1 c.c.). The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the product obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 118-19°. Mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was the same.

7-Methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin was also obtained by heating the dihydrocoumarin for one hour in an oil-bath at 155°-160° and by shaking the copper salt in an ethereal suspension with 10% sulphuric acid for about 20 minutes.

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3:4:5-trimethyl-3:4-dihydrocoumarin (III, R=Me).—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (2 g.) and ethyl propionate (6 g.) were added to pulverised sodium (0.6 g.) and refluxed in an oil bath at 110°-120° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the solid obtained on acidification was crystallised

from rectified spirit in shining plates (0.7 g.), m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 66.1; H, 6.8. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 6.8 per cent). The product gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *copper salt*, prepared as before, was crystallised from benzene, in which it was sparingly soluble, in deep green tiny needles, m.p. 193-96°. (Found: C, 58.7; H, 6.1. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4Cu$ requires C, 58.5; H, 5.6 per cent).

The above dihydrocoumarin (III, R=Me; 0.3 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and refluxed with hydrochloric acid (conc., 1 c.c.) for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in tiny needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 90-92°. Mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-3:4:5-trimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethyl-3:4-dihydrocoumarin (III, R=Et).—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (4 g.) and ethyl butyrate (10 g.) were added to pulverised sodium (1 g.) and refluxed in an oil-bath at 110°-120° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the solid obtained on acidification was crystallised from rectified spirit in thin shining plates (1 g.), m.p. 130-32°. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 7.2. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2 per cent). The product gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *copper salt*, prepared as before, was crystallised from benzene, in which it was sparingly soluble, in deep green tiny needles, m.p. 205-208°. (Found: Cu, 11.2. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 11.3 per cent).

The above dihydrocoumarin (III, R=Et; 0.2 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1.5 c.c.) and refluxed with a few drops of hydrochloric acid (conc.) for about 15 minutes. The product obtained on dilution with water was crystallised from rectified spirit in colorless rectangular prisms, m.p. 79-81°. Mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

Molecular Rearrangement of Orcacetophenone Diacetate: 7-Hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin.—Orcacetophenone diacetate, prepared from orcacetophenone (Hoesch, *loc. cit.*) (3 g.), acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) and a few drops of pyridine by refluxing for 5 hours. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pinkish white needles (2 g.), m.p. 72-73°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 5.6. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6 per cent).

Orcacetophenone diacetate (3 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (45 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.6 g.) and the reaction mixture heated for 4 hours between 120° and 130° in an oil-bath. At the end of that period the reaction mixture was cooled and the unreacted sodium was dissolved in alcohol cautiously. The sodium salt was filtered and decomposed with dilute acetic acid. The product which came down was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles (1.1 g.), m.p. 213°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin, prepared according to Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*), was not depressed.

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 263°. Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 250-260° (d). The *acetyl derivative* was prepared as usual and crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 125-26°. Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

The above coumarin of m.p. 213° (0.2 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (5%, 10 c.c.) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The product which separated on acidification was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. $254-55^{\circ}$. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin, prepared according to Sethna and Shah (*loc. cit.*), was not depressed.

Molecular Rearrangement of Orcacetophenone Dibenzoate to 7-Hydroxy-5-methylflavone.—The dibenzoate was prepared from orcacetophenone (3 g.), dissolved in pyridine, and benzoyl chloride (3.5 c.c.) by heating on a water-bath for 3 hours. The solid which separated on pouring the reaction mixture in cold hydrochloric acid was collected, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and then crystallised from dilute alcohol in pinkish white needles (4 g.), m.p. $97-98^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 73.6; H, 4.9. $C_{22}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 73.8; H, 4.8 per cent).

Orcacetophenone dibenzoate (3 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (30 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.4 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours at $120-130^{\circ}$. The sodium salt which remained after dissolving the unreacted sodium in alcohol was filtered and decomposed with dilute acetic acid. The product obtained was filtered and crystallised from rectified spirit in pale brown needles (0.54 g.), m.p. 312° . Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-4-methylflavone, prepared according to Sethna and Shah (*this Journal*, 1940, 17, 603), was not depressed.

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